

Supplementary Data (Jenner et al. 2025)

(North)western blotting

Proteins were prepared and purified according to the description presented previously. Samples were resolved on a 12.5% SDS-PAGE gel, then transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes using a wet transfer system Miniprotean (Biorad) at constant current (350 mA) for 90 minutes. The transfer buffer consisted of 25 mM Tris, 192 mM glycine, and 20% methanol. Post-transfer, the membranes were stained with 0.1% Ponceau S (Carl Roth GmbH) for protein visualization, followed by destaining with deionized water until clear. To renature proteins, membranes were incubated in renaturation buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5; 50 mM NaCl; 1 mM EDTA; 0.02% [w/v] Ficoll 400; 0.02% [w/v] polyvinylpyrrolidone-40; 1% [w/v] BSA) for one hour at room temperature with gentle shaking. The membranes were then washed three times with Northwestern (NW) buffer (renaturation buffer without BSA). Membranes were incubated in hybridization boxes with NW buffer containing ³²P radiolabelled RNA and competitor RNA, where noted, either in vitro-synthesised control RNA or commercial tRNA from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (R5636, Sigma Aldrich). Incubation was carried out for two hours or overnight at room temperature with gentle shaking or rolling. Unbound RNA was then removed by washing the membranes 3–4 times with NW buffer for 10 minutes each. Following this, membranes were air-dried, wrapped in plastic foil, and exposed on an imaging desk (GE Healthcare). A Typhoon FLA 9000 phosphorimager (GE Healthcare) was then used to visualise bound ³²P-labelled RNA.

For western blotting, the same procedure was followed until the Ponceau S destaining step. After this, membranes were blocked with 5% fat-free milk powder in 50 mM Tris-HCl, 150 mM NaCl, pH 8. They were incubated with 1:5000 diluted anti-GST primary antibodies (G1160, Sigma Aldrich) in the same buffer overnight, washed three times for 10 minutes with buffer only. Next, they were incubated with 1:8000 anti-mouse horseradish peroxidase fusion secondary antibodies (A0168, Sigma Aldrich) in the same buffer for 1 hour, washed three times as before and then visualised using a SuperSignal™ West Femto Maximum Sensitivity kit (#34096, Thermo Scientific) diluting the substrate 1:1 with water and then visualising chemiluminescence using an Amersham™ Imager 680 (GE Healthcare).

Fluorescence Spectroscopy

Fluorescence-monitored titrations were recorded using a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer (Agilent) and a 0.4 cm micro cuvette. Samples were prepared in 20 nM AtTR-Cy5 in 50 mM Tris-HCl, 250 mM NaCl, 250 mM potassium acetate, pH 7 with 0.05% Tween, titrated with AtLa1 as indicated in figure annotations. Emission spectra were recorded using 625 nm as the excitation wavelength and 10 nm excitation and emission slit widths and then plotted in QTIplot (IonDev Software), accounting for baseline drift and dilution.

Yeast protein expression analysis

Yeast cells were grown to OD~2.5 and lysed by incubation in 0.1 M NaOH for 5 min and boiling in SDS Laemmli buffer (62.5 mM Tris-HCl, 2% SDS, 5% β-mercaptoethanol, 10% glycerol, 0.002% bromophenol blue; (1)). Samples were separated by 12% SDS-PAGE, blotted, and analysed with anti-myc-HRP (Abcam 62928) diluted to 1:5000 in 1% milk-TBST, and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature. After washing in TBST buffer, chemiluminescence was detected using SuperSignal™ West Dura Extended Duration Substrate (#34075, Thermo Scientific).

Small angle X-ray scattering

3 mg/mL AtLa1 or 1 mg/mL xRRM were purified with a 6x His tag to avoid contributions from globular fusion protein GST. SAXS data were collected using a Rigaku BioSAXS-2000 instrument at CEITEC (Brno, Czech Republic) equipped with a HyPix-3000 detector at a sample-detector distance of 0.48 m. Scattered intensity was measured in the range 0.009-0.65 $1/\text{\AA}$, where $q = 4\pi \sin \theta/\lambda$; 2θ is the scattering angle and $\lambda = 0.154$ nm. The datasets were normalized to the intensity of the transmitted beam and radially averaged using SAXSLab (Rigaku). Scattering curves from individual frames were checked for radiation damage and averaged. The corresponding scattering from the solvent-blank was subtracted to produce scattering profiles, which were then analysed using PRIMUS from the ATSAS 4.1:1-1 toolset (EMBL, Hamburg) to visualise data as a Kratky plot to evaluate protein folding. For further analysis, SAXS data were truncated from the first Guinier point to a maximum of $q = 0.3$ $1/\text{\AA}$. EOM software (2) was used to fit theoretical scattering from ensembles of AlphaFold-derived models to experimental data. The SAXS datasets and experimental details were deposited at SASBDB under the accession codes: SASDYP2 and SASDYQ2.

Figure S1 AtLa1 purification and AtLa1-TR binding extended data. (A) Example Coomassie blue stained 12.5% SDS PAGE image showing purified GST-fused AtLa1 proteins used in this study. **(B)** Example anti-GST western blotting of a non-stained replicate of (A), 23 kDa species detected in most blots (but not typically in Coomassie gels of fresh protein) is assigned as traces of free GST. **(C)** Representative northwestern blotting of AtLa1 with C-terminal GST or 6x His, showing general Ponceau S staining of blotted proteins (left panel) and detection of radioactively labelled AtTR bound to AtLa1 (right panel) in the presence of non-labelled yeast tRNA (tRNA) or pCDT1a competitors with molar excesses as indicated. **(D)** Representative full EMSA image using 1% agarose gels, 80 nM AtTR 1-268 (upper two rows), 1-262 (lower two rows), and AtLa1 fragments as annotated with concentrations in nM, visualised by fluorescent staining. Parts of this image are used in Figures 2B, 2D. **(E)** Representative band shift of 40 nM RNA caused by binding of AtLa1 FL (concentrations in nM) as visualised in agarose gel by fluorescent staining.

Figure S2 Microscale thermophoresis (MST) for protein-RNA binding experiments. **(A)** Raw MST traces from representative AtLa1 to AtTR-Cy5 binding in premium coated capillaries to reduce aggregation, annotated to visualise calculation of initial fluorescence and thermophoresis values. **(B)** MST detection limits of serially-diluted AtTR. (Left panel) thermophoresis of AtTR only, at a range of different absolute fluorescence values. Black lines show the linear region where no artefactual ΔF is detected, with colours indicating time point of thermophoresis from 1.5 s (T-jump) to 20 s (i.e., 1.5, 2.5, 5, 10, 15, 20). (Right panel) raw data of the same experiment with coloured lines to indicate time points for analysis. Black MST traces are from the reliable linear dependence region, red traces show artefactual ΔF and noise where initial fluorescence is <1000 or lack of detectable thermophoresis where fluorescence is >250000 . **(C)** Initial fluorescence values in AtLa1 to AtTR-Cy5 binding MST experiments compared with other techniques. Open black circles with dashed lines are normalised fluorescence emission at 680 nm from 20 nM AtTR-Cy5, with excitation at 625 nm using a traditional spectrofluorometer, full spectra shown in **(D)**. Closed red circles show normalised $\Delta\epsilon$ at 265 nm from circular dichroism experiments monitoring 50 nM unlabelled AtTR, spectra and difference spectra shown in **(E)**. **(F)** MST initial fluorescence (upper panel) and T-jump (lower panel) of AtTERT TR binding domain (TRBD) and AtLa1 with 3' or 5' Cy5-labelled AtTR 1-268. Solid lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D (Table S3), dotted line is a Hill equation fit with $n=2$ to the fast initial fluorescence change for comparison, error bars are standard deviation. as annotated. **(G)** Schema of partial AtTERT binding to AtTR, showing alternative positions of Cy5 fluorophores (red stars) as annotated and possible region of 5'Cy5 inhibition of AtLa1 binding (grey dashed circle).

Figure S3 Conservation of xRRM domains. (A) True La and LARP7 xRRM domain sequence alignment after the style of (3). Annotations show positions of beta sheets (arrows) and alpha helices (zig-zags) with conserved RNA-interacting residues coloured as in Figure 2. The xRRM-specific RNP3 motif is also annotated, as are approximate positions of missing canonical RRM motifs RNP1 and RNP2. (B, C) Radially averaged small angle X-ray scattering data (dots), presented as (B) a Kratky plot or (C) fitted to theoretical scattering from structural ensembles (grey lines) calculated by EOM software (2) either AtLa1 FL (black dots, $\chi^2 = 1.431$, SASDYP2) or xRRM (red dots, $\chi^2 = 1.190$, SASDYQ2). (D, E) Structural ensembles of (D) AtLa1 FL or (E) xRRM models corresponding to (A). For one model of each ensemble, domains shown are xRRM (red, fixed) and LaM (grey, mobile), plus unstructured linker (black, mobile), with all other models in white. For (E) RNA-implicated residues are shown as sticks

and coloured as per Figure 2A. Further details in Table S6 and SASBDB. **(F)** Alphafold3 (4) prediction of AtLa1 xRRM domain (white) overlaid with experimental models of xRRM domains from fission yeast Pof8 (PDB - 6TZN, grey, 53 paired residues after pruning, RMSD = 0.805 Å) and *Tetrahymena* p65 (PDB - 8GAP, black, 33 paired residues after pruning, RMSD = 0.939 Å) using the ChimeraX Matchmaker tool (5). Conserved RNA-binding residues are annotated with AtLa1 numbering and colours as in Figure 2. Structural visualisations were prepared using ChimeraX (5). **(G)** Alphafold3 model of *Tetrahymena* Mlp1 showing conserved La motif (grey), predicted xRRM (red) overlaid with predicted AtLa1 xRRM (dark grey), and DUF3223 (yellow) overlaid with predicted AtDomino (green) structures.

Figure S4 AtLa1 binding to variant AtTR constructs. **(A)** Yeast three-hybrid experiments pairing AtTERT constructs, as annotated with MS2-tagged AtTR constructs as annotated, according to (6). Numbers refer to mM concentrations of 3-aminotriazole in growth media, letters refer to amino acids absent for growth. **(B)** ELISA competition experiments detecting immunolabelled AtLa1 bound to ≤ 0.5 pmol biotinylated AtTR 1-268 and non-biotinylated competitor RNA as annotated, with data reproduced from Figure 1D for comparison. Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D , error bars represent the standard deviation. For competition ELISAs, fittings were used to calculate K_D values in Figure 3G. **(C)** 2-dimensional structure of the AtTR TWJ and P4/5/6 stem, modelled after that proposed in (7) with ggg179 marked in red, gg185 marked in purple, and gg193 and gg196 sequences marked in blue. **(D)** MST T-jump data of AtLa1 FL with Cy5-labelled point variants as annotated, with colour scheme as (C). Solid lines are equations used to calculate K_D values, error bars are standard deviation, AtTR 1-268 data reproduced from Figure 1F for comparison.

Figure S5 – Extended data on protein-protein, RNA-protein and multicomponent protein-RNA interactions. (A-C) Yeast 2-hybrid assays pairing Gal4 binding domain (BD) fused AtLa1 fragments and variants with Gal4 activation domain (AD) fused (A) AtDomino or (B) AtDomino-delC. Representative anti-BD western blotting of yeast cultures as indicated used for 2-hybrid experiments (C), proteins extracted according to (1). Data shown in Figure 4B is taken from (A). (D) MST 1.5 s T-jump data of AtDomino with 5 nM 3' Cy5-labelled AtTR fragments as annotated. Lines show equations fit to data used to calculate K_D , error bars are standard deviation, AtDomino-AtTR 1-268 data are reproduced from Figure 4F. (E) Schematic of the multicomponent yeast 3-hybrid experiment. Coloured shapes represent proteins, line structures represent RNA (black lines) or DNA (red and blue lines), upper panel is with empty BD and lower panel is in the presence of TR-interacting AtLa1 (blue shape).

Table S1. Oligonucleotides used for cloning, mutagenesis, and in PCR for in vitro synthesis

Name	note		sequence (5'-3')
RNA probes			
uuu			[Cy5] CCAAAUAAUUU
ccc			[Cy5]_CCAAAUACCC
Plant TRs			
Slycopersicum-R8_Fw	cloning	Eva-C251	AGGGGGTGTGGAGCTGAGATCAAT
Slycopersicum-R8_Rev	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C252	GGAGGTGCTGGCAAGCGAG
Cestrum-R8_Fw	cloning	Eva-C253	CTCGGGGGTGTGGTGTGAGTACTG
Cestrum-R8_Rev	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C254	GGGGTGTGGCAAGCAAGGAAAC
PisumR8_Fw1	cloning	Eva-C243	CAGTTTATAGGAGGCTCGCACAAC
PisumR8_Rev1	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C244	CATTATCTAAAATAGTGGTGGGGTATGGG
AsparagusR8_Fw1	cloning	Eva-C245	AGGGGATGGTGGGCCGTG
AsparagusR8_Rev1	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C246	GGGGGATGGTGTTTAAGTGAGGC
ZmR8_Fw1	cloning	Eva-C247	CCAGAGGGTGAAGTGCATTGGAGT
ZmR8_Rev1	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C248	TGAGGGGGTGCAGCTGGAAG
RNA constructs			
U6.26F	cloning	Eva-C180	AGGGGACATCCGATAAAAATTGGAAC
U6.26R	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C181	TGCAAAAAAATTTGGACCATTCTCGAT
MRP1_RNA_Fw	cloning	Eva-C184	AATTGTCACTGGACGAAGTGAA
MRP1_RNA_Rev	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C185	TTGTCATTGAAACGTAAGCCC
MRP_RNA_Rev2	cloning,	Eva-	CGACGAAAGAAAAAGTTGCTTGTGATTGAAACGT

	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	C293	
ATR-5UTR_Fwclon	cloning	Eva-C177	AGCGGAAAAACCAGTTAAACCCTT
ATR-5UTR_Rev	cloning, PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C178	TTCACAATCGCAGAAGCTCTC
T7-U6.26F	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C182	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGGGGACATCCGATAAAATTGGAAC
T7_MRP1_RNA_Fw	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C186	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGCAATTGTCCTGGACGAAGTGAA
pCDT1a_T7-1_Fw	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C135	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGTCGTTTCAGAGACAGCAATTCATAAT
promCDT1a-ATGRev	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C119	GTGTACTCATTTTTATCAACAATGTCT
F_up_pretsnoR43.1	cloning	Eva-C300	CATAGCGTAAGGTTCAACAAAGC
R_dw_pretsnoR43.1	cloning	Eva-C299	GCAGGCTATTTTGGCAGATAC
T7_pretsnoR43.1	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C301	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGCACCACTGGTCTAGTG
R_pU_pretsnoR43.1	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C304	AAAAATAGAGCTCAGAGTAGGC
R_pretsnoR43.1	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C303	GAGCTCAGAGTAGGCGAAATC
T7_snoR43.1	PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis	Eva-C302	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGTGAGCTGTGATGAAATTGGCTT
Arabidopsis TR mutagenesis			
uATR8d201-31	cloning, delta P6	Eva-C290	CGTAGGTGGTTGAAAAACCGTTTCTCGCCTTACC
dATR8d201-31	cloning, delta P6	Eva-C289	GAAACGGTTTTTCAACCACCTACGAACCAAACC
U_ATR8_gg179cc	site mutagenesis	Eva-M15	aagtagaccaggaggttcggttcgtaggtgg
d_ATR8_gg179cc	site mutagenesis	Eva-M16	ccacctcgaaccaaaggaacctcctggtctactt
U_ATR8_ggg179cac	site mutagenesis	Eva-M25	caaaaagtagaccaggaggttcactttggttcgtaggtggtctg
d_ATR8_ggg179cac	site mutagenesis	Eva-M26	cagaaccacctcgaaccaaagtgacctcctggtctacttttg

U_ATR8 _gg193cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M19	caggaggttggtttggttcgtacctggttctgtga
d_ATR8 _gg193cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M20	tcaacagaaccaggtacgaaccaaaccacacctctg
U_ATR8 _gg196cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M21	gttgggtttggttcgtaggtccttctgttgaactagattag
d_ATR8 _gg196cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M22	ctaactagtttcaacagaaggacctacgaaccaaaccac
U_ATR8 _gg185cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M17	gaccaggaggttggtttccttctgtaggtggttctg
d_ATR8 _gg185cc	site mutagene sis	Eva- M18	cagaaccacctacgaaggaaaccacacctctggtc
Arabidopsis TR constructs (PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis)			
ATR8_T7-1_Fw		Eva- C98	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAAGGGGTGTGGGAACCTAG
ATR8_T7-26_Fw		Eva- C99	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAGTCTGCTTATTGATTGC
ATR8_T7-178_Fw		Eva- C100	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGTTGGGTTTGGTTCGTAGGTG
ATR8_T7-D19- 171_Fw		Eva- C183	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGGAAGGGGTGTGGGAACCTAAGGAGGTTGG GTTTGGTTCCG
ATR8_REV1		Eva- C86	AAATATTTGGGGGTGGGAGGGTAA
ATR8_152_Rev		Eva- C103	AGCCTCTTATGTAGCCATCGA
ATR8_251_Rev		Eva- C102	AGGGTAAGGCGAGGAAACGGT
ATR8_262_Rev		Eva- C239	TTTGGGGGTGGGAGGGTAAG
ATR8_Rev_Jap		Eva- C240	GGGGGTGGGAGGGTAAGG
ATR8_245_Rev		Eva- C288	AAGGCGAGGAAACGGTTAACCC
ATR8_dP4_Rev		dP4_R ev	TTTGGGGGTGGGAGAGGA
ATR8-Rev_ter3		Eva- C121	GATGTAAAAACCATCATTACTTAAAATAA
ATR8-Rev_ter3B		Eva- C153	AAAAACCATCATTACTTAAAATAAAAAATAG
ATR8-Rev_ter2		Eva- C122	CTTAAAATAAAAAATAGAAAACAAAATATTTGGG
ATR8-Rev_ter2B		Eva- C154	AAAATAAAAAATAGAAAACAAAATATTTGGGG
ATR8-Rev_ter1		Eva- C123	ATAGAAAACAAAATATTTGGGGGTG
ATR8-Rev_ter1B		Eva- C155	AAAACAAAATATTTGGGGGTGGGA

universal PCR for in vitro RNA synthesis			
M13F	universal		GTTTTCCAGTCACGA
Preparation of Y3H constructs			
prBS062	$\Delta T/PK$ and $\Delta P6$		GGCTAGAAGTGGATCCCCGGGAAGGGGTGTGGGAACCTAGG
prBS063	$\Delta T/PK$ and $\Delta P6$		CCTGCAGGCATGCAAGCTGCCCGGAAATATTTGGGGTGGGAGGG
prBS047	AtTR1-268		CCGGCTAGAAGTGGATCCCCGGGGGTTTGGTTCTGATAGTGG
prBS031	AtTR1-268		CCTGCAGGCATGCAAGCTGCCCGGAGGGTAAGGCGAGGAAACG
Protein constructs and fragments			
F_LA1_GW		Lada-125	AAAAAGCAGGCTACATGTCGATTCCTTGTCTAACCG
R_LA1+GW		Lada-126	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTCATGCTTCCACCTTCTGAGA
F_LA1_pGEX4T3		Eva-C138	GTGGATCCCCGAATCCATGTCGATTCCTTGTCTAACCG
R_LA1_pGEX-3		Eva-C132	GTCGACCCGGGAATTTGCTTCCACCTTCTGAGATTTG
F-La1_delN_pB1		Eva-G218	AAAAAGCAGGCTACAAAGAAGAAAAGGGTGTCTAGC
R-La1_delC(+)_pB2		Eva-G219	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTATTTCTCATCATCTTCATCCTCTGC
F-La1_G236_pB1		Eva-G241	AAAAAGCAGGCTACGGTTTGATCATTTTCATTCACCTC
R-La1_G236(+)_pB2		Eva-G242	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTAACCTTGGGATAATCTGGCTCAT
R-La1_A206(+)_pB2		Eva-G243	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTAAGCAAATTTACTTCATCCTTCTCC
R-La1_R116(+)_pB2		Eva-G244	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTATCTAGCATTAAAGTTGCTCAATCAA
F-La1_L106_pB1		Eva-G245	AAAAAGCAGGCTACCTGGAAGATTTGATTGAGCAACTT
F-DOMINO1_gw		Eva-G95	AAAAAGCAGGCTACATGGCTGAAGAACAAGAGATCG
R-DOMINO1+gw		Eva-G96	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTCATCTTCTGAATCTCCCTCCTC
DOMINO1_delC_pB2		Eva-G280	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTAAGGCAATGGGAGGATTTGATC
La1 mutagenesis			
U_La1-F331A		Eva-M1	cagatcccatcttgaatcaacagccttgacatcaccaaatttccga
d_La1-F331A		Eva-M2	tcgaaaatttggtgatgtcaaggctgttgattcaagatgggatctg
U_La1-D333R		Eva-M5	cgtctcagatcccatcttgaacgaacaaacttgacatcaccaaat
d_La1-D333R		Eva-M6	atttggtgatgtcaagttgttcgtttcaagatgggatctgagacg
U_La1-R344A		Eva-M7	atgcttcaggttcatcaaacgaagataaccgtctcagatc
d_La1-R344A		Eva-	gatctgagacgggttatcttgcgtttgatgaacctgaagcat

		M8	
U_La1-W387A		Eva-M9	ttgcttcgtaggagagtcgcatactcctttcagcttcgc
d_La1-W387A		Eva-M10	gcgaagctgaaaaggagatgcgactctcctacgaagcaa
dLa124SYD-GGG		Eva-M47	gattccacgtctcccttttaacaccaccgccgaaagtgacgcagctactgttctagc
uLa124SYD-GGG		Eva-M48	gctagaacagtagctgcgtcaccttcggcgggtggtttaaagggaagacgtggaatc
dLa1156G		Eva-M49	tcatgttgacagagtcgaggggattttctggtgttccttg
uLa1156G		Eva-M50	caaggcaacaccagaaaatcccctcgactctgcaacatga
dLaQ184G		Eva-M51	agaatttggctttgctggtggggagttggagctgaaacc
uLaQ184G		Eva-M52	ggttcagctccaactccccaccagcaaagaccaattct

Table S2. K_D values (nM) from ELISA competition experiments. All experiments used immunodetection of GST-fused La1 FL bound to immobilised 3' biotinylated AtTR 1-268 and displaced by the presence of unlabelled competitor as indicated.

Variable Competitor				Variable Competitor			
RNA	ELISA	Ratio vs 1-268	replicas	AtTR	ELISA	Ratio vs 1-268	replicas
AtTR	41 ± 6	1.00	2	1-245	9 ± 3	0.22	2
pre-tsnoR43.1	150 ± 40	3.66	2	1-251	50 ± 20	1.22	2
pre-tsnoR43.1ΔU	100 ± 30	2.44	2	1-259	52 ± 9	1.27	2
snoR43.1	14 ± 3	0.34	2	0-274	90 ± 20	2.20	2
snoR43.1 ΔU	70 ± 10	1.71	2	0-277	70 ± 10	1.71	2
ytRNA	220 ± 30	5.37	2	0-286	90 ± 20	2.20	2
MRP1	160 ± 40	3.90	2	0-289	25 ± 5	0.61	2
MRP1 ΔU	130 ± 40	3.17	2	0-304	13 ± 3	0.32	2
U6-26	260 ± 80	6.34	2	0-309	32 ± 9	0.78	2
ATR 5'UTR	600 ± 200	14.63	2	T/PK	190 ± 40	4.63	2
				ΔT/PK	70 ± 10	1.71	2
				ΔP4	70 ± 10	1.71	2
				ΔP6	80 ± 20	1.95	2
				P4/5/6	500 ± 100	12.20	2
				ΔU	58 ± 9	1.41	2

Plant TR Competitor	Telomere repeat	ELISA	Ratio vs 1-268	replicas
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	TTTAGGG	41 ± 6	1.00	2
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	TTTAGGG	30 ± 10	0.73	2
<i>Asparagus officinalis</i>	TTAGGG	50 ± 10	1.22	2
<i>Allium cepa</i>	CTCGGTTATGGG	50 ± 10	1.22	2
<i>Nicotiana sylvestris</i>	TTTAGGG	42 ± 9	1.02	2
<i>Scilla peruviana</i>	TTAGGG	80 ± 30	1.95	2
<i>Zea mays</i>	TTTAGGG	60 ± 20	1.46	2
<i>Cestrum elegans</i>	TTTTTTAGGG	90 ± 20	2.20	2
<i>Pisum sativum</i>	TTTAGGG	80 ± 20	1.95	2

Table S3. Full details of K_D values from MST experiments. Processes Fluor 1 and Fluor 2 are fast and slow initial fluorescence changes. MST values are calculated from the first 1.5 s of thermophoresis (T-jump) fast (1) and slow (2) processes. Error values are from K_D fittings, some data are replicated from Table 1 for completeness.

Protein	AtTR	K_D at 25 °C				Ratio vs AtTR 1-268				replicas
		Fluor 1 (nM)	Fluor 2 (μ M)	MST 1 (nM)	MST 2(μ M)	Fluor 1	Fluor 2	MST 1	MST2	
AtLa1 FL	1-268	5 \pm 1	1.9 \pm 0.2	20 \pm 10	0.65 \pm 0.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	5
	mP2/3	1 \pm 0.3	0.54 \pm 0.1	5 \pm 2	0.5 \pm 0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.8	1
	T/PK	21 \pm 2	90 \pm 30	1000 \pm 200		4.2	47.4	50.0		1
	ΔT/PK	2.7 \pm 0.7	1.4 \pm 0.1	16 \pm 7	1.4 \pm 0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	2.2	1
	ΔP4	38 \pm 4	35 \pm 6	560 \pm 70		7.6	18.4	28.0		1
	ΔP6	16 \pm 6	8.1 \pm 0.7	130 \pm 30		3.2	4.3	6.5		1
	P4/5/6	6 \pm 3	3 \pm 0.2	34 \pm 9	4 \pm 0.2	1.2	1.6	1.7	6.2	1
	ΔU	12 \pm 2	2.4 \pm 0.3	70 \pm 10		2.4	1.3	3.5		2
AtLa1 LaM	1-268	130 \pm 10	41 \pm 3	1200 \pm 300	70 \pm 30	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	3
	mP2/3	12 \pm 3	9.4 \pm 0.3	70 \pm 40	2.6 \pm 0.3	0.1	0.2	0.1	4.0	1
	T/PK	5 \pm 1	10 \pm 1	170 \pm 20		0.0	0.2	0.1		1
	ΔT/PK	340 \pm 70	140 \pm 30	2000 \pm 500		2.6	3.4	1.7		1
	ΔP4	170 \pm 40	80 \pm 10	2100 \pm 300		1.3	2.0	1.8		1
	ΔP6	13 \pm 3	5.6 \pm 0.9	30 \pm 20	3.1 \pm 0.7	0.1	0.1	0.0	4.8	1
	P4/5/6	130 \pm 30	8 \pm 2	600 \pm 100	18 \pm 4	1.0	0.2	0.5	27.7	1
	ΔU	4 \pm 1	5.6 \pm 0.8	20 \pm 10	2.6 \pm 0.4	0.0	0.1	0.0	4.0	1
AtLa1 xRRM	1-268	28 \pm 3	6 \pm 1	220 \pm 30		1.0	1.0	1.0		2
	mP2/3	3 \pm 1	2.6 \pm 0.5	19 \pm 8	1 \pm 0.1	0.1	0.4	0.1	1.5	1
	T/PK	18 \pm 5	30 \pm 5	590 \pm 90		0.6	5.0	2.7		1
	ΔT/PK	4 \pm 1	2.3 \pm 0.2	28 \pm 5	1.4 \pm 0.6	0.1	0.4	0.1	2.2	1
	ΔP4	4 \pm 1	2.4 \pm 0.3	40 \pm 10	2.1 \pm 0.8	0.1	0.4	0.2	3.2	1
	ΔP6	4 \pm 1	1.4 \pm 0.2	14 \pm 7	1 \pm 0.7	0.1	0.2	0.1	1.5	1
	P4/5/6	18 \pm 5	7.6 \pm 0.9	90 \pm 30	8 \pm 1	0.6	1.3	0.4	12.3	1
	ΔU	4 \pm 1	1.4 \pm 0.3	20 \pm 10	0.18 \pm 0	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	1
AtLa1 F331A	1-268	8 \pm 2	1.8 \pm 0.3	24 \pm 3	3 \pm 1					4
AtLa1 D333R	1-268	3 \pm 1	1.2 \pm 0.1	29 \pm 4	0.45 \pm 0.1					3
AtLa1 R344A	1-268	48 \pm 7	14 \pm 4	550 \pm 60						2
AtLa1 W387A	1-268	40 \pm 4	2.7 \pm 0.9	230 \pm 50	4 \pm 1					2
AtLa1 FL	gg179cc	2.2 \pm 0.4	0.9 \pm 0.3	15 \pm 4	1.5 \pm 0.2	0.4	0.5	0.8	2.3	1
	ggg179cac	3 \pm 0.7	3.2 \pm 0.3	31 \pm 5	1.8 \pm 0.5	0.6	1.7	1.6	2.8	1
	gg185cc	18 \pm 4	4.6 \pm 0.6	140 \pm 30	1.2 \pm 0.2	3.6	2.4	7.0	1.8	1
	gg193cc	3.2 \pm 0.6	1.3 \pm 0.3	19 \pm 3	0.6 \pm 0.2	0.6	0.7	1.0	0.9	1
	gg196cc	3 \pm 0.7	2.9 \pm 0.3	49 \pm 8	4 \pm 1	0.6	1.5	2.5	6.2	1
AtLa1 FL	pre-tsnoR43.1	20 \pm 3	6.8 \pm 0.7	240 \pm 30		4.0	3.6	12.0		2
	pre-tsnoR43.1 ΔU	10 \pm 3	10 \pm 3	180 \pm 20		2.0	5.3	9.0		2
	tsnoR43.1	1.3 \pm 0.4	5.6 \pm 0.6	50 \pm 5	4 \pm 2	0.3	2.9	2.5	6.2	1
	tsnoR43.1 ΔU	40 \pm 10	29 \pm 7	1000 \pm 90		8.0	15.3	50.0		1
	ytRNA	100 \pm 30	17 \pm 8	1300 \pm 200		20.0	8.9	65.0		2
	MRP1	3 \pm 0.7	2.7 \pm 0.5	120 \pm 30	8 \pm 4	0.6	1.4	6.0	12.3	1

	MRP1 Δ U	5 \pm 2	1.6 \pm 0.4	53 \pm 7	9 \pm 3	1.0	0.8	2.7	13.8	1
TRBD	1-268	8 \pm 2	7 \pm 1	42 \pm 6	8 \pm 0.9					2
Domino FL	1-268	21 \pm 3	6.9 \pm 0.7	150 \pm 20	24 \pm 6	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	3
	mP2/3	21 \pm 7	14 \pm 2	150 \pm 30		1.0	2.0	1.0		1
	T/PK	5 \pm 1	10.9 \pm 0.4	130 \pm 20		0.2	1.6	0.9		1
	ΔT/PK	3.3 \pm 0.6	29 \pm 5	470 \pm 60		0.2	4.2	3.1		1
	ytRNA	1400 \pm 600	70 \pm 50	3700 \pm 600		66.7	10.1	24.7		1
Domino delC	1-268	90 \pm 20	6 \pm 2	220 \pm 50	8 \pm 4					1

Table S4. K_D values from MST experiments with competitors. ‘Additive’ indicates a constant concentration of non-labelled RNA competitor as indicated or the presence of another protein as indicated. Processes Fluor 1 and Fluor 2 are fast and slow initial fluorescence changes. MST values are calculated from the first 1.5 s of thermophoresis (T-jump) fast (1) and slow (2) processes. Error values are from K_D fittings.

Protein +Constant Competitor	Additive Competitor	Fluor 1 (nM)	Fluor 2 (μ M)	MST 1 (nM)	MST2 (μ M)	Ratio vs AtTR 1-268				
						Fluor1	Fluor 2	MST 1	MST2replicas	
FL+TR	ytRNA (100x)	9 \pm 2	0.7 \pm 0.2	310 \pm 30		1.8	0.4	15.5	1	
	ytRNA (1000x)	30 \pm 8	0.9 \pm 0.3	530 \pm 70		6.0	0.5	26.5	1	
	pre-tsnoR43.1 (10x)	60 \pm 30		700 \pm 100		12.0		35.0	1	
	pre-tsnoR43.1 ΔU (10x)	110 \pm 30		900 \pm 100		22.0		45.0	1	
LaM+TR	ytRNA (100x)	130 \pm 40	80 \pm 20	1100 \pm 100		1.0	2.0	0.9	1	
xRRM +TR	ytRNA (100x)	18 \pm 2	6 \pm 1	250 \pm 40		0.6	1.0	1.1	1	
TRBD+TR	La1 (125 nM)		0.25 \pm 0.1						1	
	La1 (1250 nM)		0.17 \pm 0.1						1	
	xRRM (125 nM)		0.6 \pm 0.1	25 \pm 3	0.6 \pm 0.3		0.1	0.6	0.1	1
Domino+TR	ytRNA (1000x)	5 \pm 2	3 \pm 1	690 \pm 70		0.2	0.4	4.6	1	
	La1 (125 nM)		2.7 \pm 0.6	200 \pm 50			0.4	1.3	1	
	La1 (1250 nM)		0.9 \pm 0.3	130 \pm 90			0.1	0.9	1	
	xRRM (63 nM)		0.6 \pm 0.1	180 \pm 40			0.1	1.2	1	
	SYD (63 nM)	8 \pm 2	3.6 \pm 0.8	220 \pm 20	40 \pm 20		0.4	0.5	1.5	1.7

Table S5. Gaussian fittings to deconvoluted mass photometry spectra. Peak numberings are from low to high mass, σ indicates peak width, % is the percentage of particles covered by the fitting. * indicates that samples were prepared in high concentration as noted and an unknown tiny amount was transferred to the final drop using the so-called tip method (see Methods).

Sample	Peak1 (kDa)	σ	%	Peak2 (kDa)	σ	%	Peak3 (kDa)	σ	%	Peak4 (kDa)	σ	%
AtLa1 (5 nM)	55	10.4	82	82	14.6	17	117	9.6	4			
AtLa1 (5 nM) +Domino (50 nM)	53	11.3	65	76	13.4	41	112	11.7	7	137	20	7

Table S6. Summary of integral SAXS structural parameters.

Sample code	<i>SASDYQ2 (xRRM)</i>	<i>SASDYP2 (AtLa1)</i>
Data Collection Parameters		
Instrument	BioSAXS-2000	BioSAXS-2000
Wavelength [Å]	1.54	1.54
q range [Å ⁻¹]	0.009 – 0.65	0.009 – 0.65
Exposure time [min]	60	60
Temperature [°C]	20	9
pH	8.0	8.0
Concentration [mg ml ⁻¹]	1.0	3.0
Structural parameters		
R _g [Å] (from Guinier)	26.14	49.52
R _g [Å] (from P(r))	28.59	44.79
D _{max} [Å]	107.2	132.6
Porod volume estimate [Å ³]	24157	110848
M _w from sequence [kDa]	22.1	48.1
Primus M _w estimation [kDa]	12	94.2

References

1. Kushnirov, V.V. (2000) Rapid and reliable protein extraction from yeast. *Yeast*, **16**, 857-860.
2. Tria, G., Mertens, H.D., Kachala, M. and Svergun, D.I. (2015) Advanced ensemble modelling of flexible macromolecules using X-ray solution scattering. *IUCrJ*, **2**, 207-217.
3. Basu, R., Eichhorn, C.D., Cheng, R., Peterson, R.D. and Feigon, J. (2021) Structure of *S. pombe* telomerase protein Pof8 C-terminal domain is an xRRM conserved among LARP7 proteins. *RNA Biol*, **18**, 1181-1192.
4. Abramson, J., Adler, J., Dunger, J., Evans, R., Green, T., Pritzel, A., Ronneberger, O., Willmore, L., Ballard, A.J., Bambrick, J. *et al.* (2024) Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3. *Nature*, **630**, 493-500.
5. Pettersen, E.F., Goddard, T.D., Huang, C.C., Meng, E.C., Couch, G.S., Croll, T.I., Morris, J.H. and Ferrin, T.E. (2021) UCSF ChimeraX: Structure visualization for researchers, educators, and developers. *Protein Sci*, **30**, 70-82.
6. Stefanovie, B., Jenner, L.P., Bozdechova, L., Fajkus, P., Sykorova, E., Fajkus, J. and Palecek, J.J. (2024) Characterisation of the *Arabidopsis thaliana* telomerase TERT-TR complex. *Plant Mol Biol*, **114**, 56.
7. Song, J., Logeswaran, D., Castillo-Gonzalez, C., Li, Y., Bose, S., Aklilu, B.B., Ma, Z., Polkhovskiy, A., Chen, J.J. and Shippen, D.E. (2019) The conserved structure of plant telomerase RNA provides the missing link for an evolutionary pathway from ciliates to humans. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, **116**, 24542-24550.